

Table 11: Comparison of findings between studies

Q-Study Findings	Semi-Structured Interview Study Findings
<p>Advisors are intrinsically motivated to act in the client's best interest but feel they have too many clients to be effective fiduciaries.</p>	<p>Advisors, lacking sufficient autonomy have too many clients to serve them all well.</p>
<p>Advisors lean toward altruism and feel a personal connection with clients.</p>	<p>Lack of autonomy due to the presence of numerical targets diminishes fiduciary effectiveness.</p>
<p>Advisors believe that producing work that merely 'checks the box' to attain a sales target contradicts the proper exercise of fiduciary duty.</p>	<p>Advisors feel pressure to keep clients enrolled for whom, in their judgment, the offer is not appropriate.</p>
	<p>Advisors lean toward altruism, caring about client wellbeing.</p>
	<p>Some advisors are uneasy about having a sales role.</p>